

ELECTROMAGNETIC COMPATIBILITY TESTING FOR THE NASA LANGLEY RESEARCH CENTER BOEING 757-200

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Abstract

This paper discusses aircraft-level and laboratory electromagnetic interference (EMI) testing that has been performed for the NASA Langley Research Center (LaRC) Boeing 757-200 aircraft, called Airborne Research Integrated Experiments System (ARIES). The purpose of the testing is to determine if the research equipment causes electromagnetic interference to communication receivers and/or navigation receivers on-board the aircraft. Due to the nature of the research, experimental equipment is normally required to be cleared for all phases of flight, including takeoff and landing. Therefore, interference to the communication and navigation equipment can be considered a safety-of-flight issue. Results from several tests are presented and the potential interference concerns are identified.

Introduction

The 757 ARIES, shown in Figure 1, is being used to conduct aeronautical research. The purpose of this research is to increase aircraft safety, operating efficiency, and compatibility with future air traffic control systems. The baseline configuration of the 757 ARIES includes twelve test pallets/research workstations, which are instrumented with various types of electronic test equipment. There are additional pallets and research equipment installed depending on the research requirements [1].

The pallets contain research test equipment that range from standard avionics equipment to electronics built in-house. Although some of the research electronics have been qualified to electromagnetic compatibility (EMC) test standards, such as RTCA/DO-160, much of the research equipment has only been verified as FCC Part 15 Class A devices.

Figure 1. NASA LaRC 757 ARIES Aircraft

The purpose of the electromagnetic compatibility testing performed for the 757 ARIES is to identify any interference caused by the research equipment which could affect the operation of the communication and/or navigation receivers. The electromagnetic compatibility testing performed at NASA LaRC consists of laboratory radiated emissions testing of research equipment and aircraft-level communication/navigation receiver interference testing, which is performed once the research equipment is installed on the 757 ARIES.

757 ARIES Research Equipment

Most of the 757 ARIES research system consists of equipment installed within research pallets. The pallets are primarily located in the passenger cabin as shown in Figure 2. Other equipment is located throughout the aircraft, such as research displays mounted in the forward flight deck and a telemetry pallet located in the aft life raft overhead storage compartment. Also, there is external equipment, such as a video camera installed on the vertical stabilizer and various special-purpose antennas and sensors in other locations.

Figure 2. Example of Research Equipment/Pallet Location

The research system receives power from a power pallet located in the forward cargo bay. This pallet receives power inputs from each of the engine generators, the auxiliary power unit and external power sources. The pallet isolates 28 volts DC and 115 Volts AC, 60 Hz from the 115 Volts AC, 400 Hz bus. Also located in the forward cargo bay is an ARINC 429 isolation box, which is used to isolate any connections from the research equipment to the basic ship systems.

757 ARIES EMI Test Plan

There are different levels of EMI testing performed depending on the complexity of the research equipment and its installation. The EMI testing includes both EMC laboratory testing and aircraft-level testing. For individual pallets or equipment that do not involve complicated configurations, laboratory EMI testing may be sufficient. The laboratory EMI testing measures the research equipment's radiated emissions and the results are used to identify frequencies of potential interference in the receivers' operational bands.

The advantages of individual laboratory EMI tests are that the lab test takes less time to perform and fewer support personnel are required than an aircraft-level test. Also, the EMC laboratory is easier to schedule than obtaining test time on the 757 ARIES. A disadvantage of laboratory testing is

that it is impossible to exactly replicate the aircraft environment within the EMC laboratory. Also, the exact coupling paths to the receivers' antennas are not known. Therefore, the interference analysis considers the radiated emissions profile of the equipment and the susceptibility of the receivers but it does not account for which frequencies are most likely to couple to the receivers' antennas.

Aircraft-level testing is performed when there are major configuration changes on the 757 ARIES. The aircraft-level testing determines the interference from the research equipment to the communication and/or navigation receivers. Interference to other systems is determined during Instrumentation Check Flights (ICFs).

Configuration changes that would require aircraft-level testing include the installation of several new pallets or a complex installation involving new research equipment located throughout the aircraft and/or complex cabling. Aircraft tests would also be required if the installation location is near a receiver's antenna, such as experimental hardware located within the aircraft's nose.

The advantage of aircraft-level testing is that because the exact environment and coupling paths exist, the results are more exact. However, aircraft-level testing is resource intensive. Because the radiated emissions profile for the research system is

not known, the entire operational band must be swept for each receiver. This procedure is time consuming and may require many dedicated support personnel to operate the 757 ARIES equipment and the research pallets. However, if there are many new components added to the aircraft, one aircraft-level test will take less time than several laboratory tests.

EMC Laboratory Testing

EMC laboratory testing measures the research equipment's radiated emissions profile and compares the results to applicable limits. The primary focus of the measurement is the radiated emissions within the aircraft communication and navigation receiver's operational bands

The results of the laboratory EMI testing are used to identify frequencies of potential interference in the receivers' operational bands. If emissions of sufficient strength to potentially cause interference are found, a receiver check is performed at those frequencies after installation of the equipment.

EMC Laboratory Test Procedure

The laboratory testing is conducted in the NASA LaRC's Semi-Anechoic Electromagnetic Compatibility Test Facility. This facility is used for bench level testing of individual electronic equipment, such as laptop computers, as well as turntable testing of fully integrated pallets, as shown in Figure 3.

The test methods used for the radiated emissions testing are as per RTCA/DO-160D, Section 21 [2]. The radiated emissions are measured and compared to the radiated emissions limit for the appropriate equipment category, as defined by RTCA/DO-160D. These limits are used to identify at which frequencies the equipment's radiated emissions could potentially cause interference to the 757 ARIES communication and navigation receivers.

The measurements are made using an EMI receiver. First, a complete measurement sweep is performed to determine the overall radiated emissions profile. Then, the measurements are repeated with narrower frequency spans for the receiver operational bands used on the 757 ARIES. These radiated emissions measurements are

typically performed for all sides of a pallet with the pallet equipment operating in flight mode.

Figure 3. Radiated Emissions Testing of Experimental Aircraft Pallet in LaRC Semi-Anechoic EMC Laboratory

Analysis of Results

Using the EMI receiver's software, the measurement data is plotted against the limit line as shown in Figure 4. The software's analysis tools are then used to create a data file containing only the frequencies and signal strengths of measured emissions that exceed the limit line (exceedances). The exceedance frequencies are then compared to the tuned frequencies of the applicable receiver. The amplitude of the signal and the spacing from a tuned frequency determine how likely it is that the exceedance will cause interference to the receivers.

Figure 4. Example of GAMS pallet radiated emissions measurement results (2MHz to 6 GHz)

Mitigation of Interference

After the pallet or equipment is installed on the 757 ARIES, a receiver check is performed for the frequencies of the identified potential interference. This check involves tuning the receivers to the potential interference frequency with the research pallet or equipment powered on and determining if there is any interference noted.

This receiver check is useful for the communication receivers. The communication receivers can be operated to determine if the interference is significant enough to break the squelch. Also, the squelch can be disabled to determine if there is any discernable interference.

The correct operation of the navigation receivers is difficult to determine during ground testing. Even using a test set tuned to a frequency of concern, it is difficult to verify whether or not there is any degradation of operation due to the potential interference.

The frequencies of interference determined for the communication receivers are given to the pilots so that they may be aware of any unusable frequencies of operation. The potential interfering signals identified for the navigation receivers are noted on a chart for the pilot's awareness and are checked during the ICFs.

Example of Laboratory Testing and Results

The Gas and Aerosol Monitoring Sensorcraft (GAMS) instrument research pallet, shown in Figure 3, was tested prior to installation on the 757 ARIES. The GAMS pallet was installed in the passenger cabin. Therefore the GAMS pallet was considered category M equipment as defined by RTCA/DO-160D as "equipment and interconnected wiring located in areas where apertures are em significant and not directly in view of radio receiver's antenna" [2]. The test limits used were RTCA/DO-160D, Section 21, Category M, as shown in the plot in Figure 4.

Radiated emissions testing was performed for three sides of the GAMS pallet. One side was not tested because it was enclosed with no cables or penetrations. Figure 4 shows the measured radiated emissions profile for the frequency band of 2 MHz to 6 GHz for the aft side of the GAMS instrument. Figure 5 shows the radiated emissions measured in

the frequency band from 100 MHz to 150 MHz for the forward side of the GAMS instrument.

The limit exceedances were determined for all the measurements. Next, the potential interference frequencies were determined by identifying which frequencies were within the pass band of the receivers at tuned frequencies. A visual representation of the exceedance frequencies versus the tuned frequencies from 130 MHz to 130.5 MHz for the VHF receiver is shown in Figure 6. Based on the spacing between the exceedance frequencies and the tuned frequencies shown in the plot, the VHF receivers are more likely to receive interference at 130.00 MHz than 130.325 MHz and 130.50 MHz.

The frequencies at which interference may occur were identified using the spacing information, the 757 ARIES receivers' sensitivities and bandwidths, and the measured levels of the exceedances. This process was done for the communication receivers and the navigation receivers. The resulting list of frequencies of potential interference for the navigation receivers was reported to the 757 ARIES pilots for mitigation during ICFs.

Figure 5. GAMS radiated emissions measurement for VHF, VOR, and ILS Receiver Bands, Forward Side, Horizontal Polarization

Figure 6. Spacing of GAMS Radiated Emissions Exceedances from VHF Tuned Frequencies for Frequencies 130.00 MHz to 130.50 MHz

The list of frequencies identified as causing potential interference from the GAMS pallet to the communications receivers was used to conduct a UHF and VHF radio check after installation of the GAMS pallet onboard the 757 ARIES. The test was performed with the power pallet and the GAMS pallet powered on and all other research equipment powered off.

Each VHF and UHF receiver was tuned to the frequencies of potential interference and any interference sufficient to break squelch was noted. When possible, the squelch was also disabled to determine if any audible interference could be detected. To verify that any interference found was due to the operation of the GAMS pallet and not an external source, the pallet was powered down to ensure that the interference was not present with the GAMS pallet powered off.

Table 1 contains the results of the receiver check for the VHF Center Receiver for the GAMS pallet installation. The VHF frequencies that were identified are listed. The spacing from the exceedance and the level of the exceedance are given for each frequency.

As seen by the results, the interference found was mostly predictable. All of the potential interference identified which was at a tuned frequency (0 Hz spacing) and exceeded the limit line by more than 5 dB μ V/m caused audible interference, except for at 134.775 MHz. Also,

there were a few frequencies at which interference was noted that would not have been considered as likely to cause interference.

Table 1. Receiver Check Results for VHF Center Receiver for GAMS Pallet Installation

Frequency of Potential Interference (MHz)	Spacing from measured frequency (MHz)	Limit Exceedance (dB μ V/m)	Inter. noted ?
120.00000	0.000	14.25	Y
120.77500	0.002	0.39	N
120.95000	0.005	0.10	N
121.30000	0.000	6.08	Y
121.50000	0.000	0.61	N
121.65000	0.000	0.74	N
124.15000	0.010	0.90	N
124.17500	0.000	2.36	N
124.20000	0.000	0.24	N
124.30000	0.005	2.49	N
124.35000	0.005	0.89	N
124.42500	0.005	3.73	N
124.45000	0.000	0.88	Y
124.50000	0.010	0.62	N
124.55000	0.005	2.05	N
124.57500	0.000	1.53	N
125.00000	0.000	0.99	Y
125.10000	0.000	0.46	N
125.62500	0.010	2.26	N
125.65000	0.010	1.71	N
126.00000	0.000	8.08	Y
127.97500	0.000	1.88	N
130.00000	0.000	13.55	Y
130.32500	0.008	3.55	N
130.50000	0.005	7.72	N
133.00000	0.010	4.76	Y
134.40000	0.000	2.29	Y
134.77500	0.000	16.28	N

The results of the GAMS pallet EMI testing found that there were two limit line exceedances for the ILS Localizer band and seven for the VOR band that were determined to be potential interference signals. The frequencies were reported to the pilots. There was no interference noted during the ICFs.

There were a total of eight VHF frequencies and 14 UHF frequencies that had audible

interference determined during the receiver checks. These frequencies were also reported to the pilots.

The results show that the EMC laboratory testing is useful for determining interference. However, it is difficult to predict the exact threshold for susceptibility. Therefore, using this method and emissions limits, more frequencies may be identified than will actually cause interference. By performing the receiver checks, it can be determined which of the signals do cause interference.

A reason for potential inaccuracies is that the EMC laboratory testing is performed in a semi-anechoic chamber. The aircraft environment is not well represented due to reflecting surfaces within the aircraft. Also, the power line impedance may not be well represented in the laboratory. These differences can affect the emissions profile of the equipment and result in differences between the laboratory and the aircraft installation.

To date, there have been three other pallets tested in the EMC laboratory. The installation of these pallets will be completed in the summer of 2001. An aircraft-level test will be performed at that time. The results will provide more comparisons between the laboratory and aircraft-level testing.

EMC laboratory testing has also been performed on individual pieces of equipment. For example, the radiated emissions were measured for a laptop computer that was installed on the aircraft. The largest emissions measured for the computer were those frequencies that had been identified during an aircraft-level communication/navigation interference test, showing good agreement between the two types of testing.

Aircraft-Level Testing

Aircraft-level testing is performed after integration testing is completed for the research system configuration and flight quality assurance has inspected and closed all pallets. All pallets are in flight configuration and operating in a normal flight mode for this testing. The interference levels are measured at the antenna ports for each of the communication and navigation receivers and then the receivers are tuned to any suspect frequencies to

determine if the level is sufficient to cause interference.

Aircraft-Level Test Procedure

This test involves measuring the level of noise at the input to the receivers listed in Table 2. This test is normally performed in the LaRC hanger, typically on the weekend or at night to ensure that the hanger is "quiet". During normal working hours, radio checks of other aircraft and operation of forklifts are some of the sources of noise which prevent testing.

Table 2. Receiver Antenna Port Measurements

Receiver Measured	Frequency Range (MHz)
Marker Beacon	74.8 – 75.2
VOR	108 – 118
ILS Localizer	108.1 – 112
ILS Glideslope	328 – 335
UHF	225 – 400
VHF	118 – 138
DME	960 – 1220

The measurements are made by using the applicable aircraft receiver's antenna as the measurement antenna, therefore, the coupling paths from the research equipment to the receiver antenna are represented. Also, any emissions from the research equipment that couple onto the antenna coaxial cable will be measured.

A spectrum analyzer is used to measure the signals and a portable printer is used to output the measurement plots. The spectrum analyzer and other measurement equipment are located in the passenger cabin. A measurement coaxial cable is routed from the passenger cabin to the electronics bays where the receivers are located.

The receiver antenna's input signal coaxial cable is disconnected from the receiver. A high frequency, low loss, measurement coaxial cable is connected to the antenna coaxial cable. This measurement cable is then connected to an oscilloscope and the signal is checked to ensure that there is no DC component to the measured signal that could damage the spectrum analyzer input.

The measurement cable is then connected to the spectrum analyzer to perform the measurement.

The measurement scan of the receiver band is first performed with all research equipment powered off. The applicable receiver frequency band is scanned using the spectrum analyzer. A narrow frequency span of 500 kHz to 2 MHz is used depending on which receiver band is being measured. The resolution bandwidth and the video bandwidth are set to 1 kHz. This setting allows good resolution of the band yet the sweep time is sufficiently short. The center frequency is changed in steps so that the entire receiver band is scanned.

The types of signals that are being measured are not known. To best perform this measurement, three separate scans would be performed with the resolution bandwidth and the video bandwidth set to optimally identify and measure all three signal types: sinewaves, broadband and random [3]. This process would require the scans to be performed three times each, which would not be practical due to the additional testing time required.

The reference level of the spectrum analyzer is set to measure very low level signals. A display line is used as a limit line, which is determined by the receiver sensitivity. For example, the sensitivity of the 757 ARIES Localizer receiver is $1.0 \mu\text{V}$ [4]. Therefore, the limit used to identify potential interference signals is $0 \text{ dB}\mu\text{V}$.

At least three sweeps are made at each frequency and the display is observed. Any signals that are above the limit line and are not observed to be intentional transmitter signals are recorded and plotted. The purpose of this baseline scan is to identify any noise that is not due to the research system. Next, the measurement scan is performed with all the research equipment powered on. Any noise signals measured are compared to those recorded in the baseline scan. If the signal was not previously identified, the frequency and level are recorded and the signal plotted. Figure 7 shows a plot of a potential interference signal identified during a Left VOR receiver scan.

Figure 7. Aircraft-level Testing Sample Plot of Potential Interference Signal at 110.66 MHz for the Left VOR Receiver

Once all of the noise signals are identified for the receiver band being tested, the spectrum analyzer is set to display the signals with more resolution. Next, the research pallets are powered down one at a time while displaying each identified signal. The source of the potential interference signal is identified when the signals are not present when the equipment is powered off. Once the pallet is identified, individual equipment on the pallet is powered on and off to determine the source of the interference at the box level. The results of this testing are recorded.

This procedure is repeated for each receiver listed in Table 2. After all the potential interference is identified, a receiver check is performed as described previously. The receiver check determines which potential interference signals are of sufficient strength to cause interference to the communication receivers. These frequencies of interference and the source of interference are reported to the pilots so that they are aware of any unusable communication frequencies.

As stated before, it is difficult to determine interference to the navigation receivers during the receiver checks. Therefore, all frequencies of potential interference to the navigation receivers are reported to the pilots and the sources of the interference are noted so that the pilots are aware at what frequencies the receivers may experience interference.

The correct operation of the navigation receivers at the identified potential interference frequencies is verified during the ICFs. Interference to other critical/essential systems is determined by performing a functional check of critical and essential systems. A functional check of as many operational modes as possible for the applicable phases of flight is performed for each of the systems listed in Table 3.

Table 3. Critical/Essential Aircraft Systems/Equipment List

System	LRU
Air	Cabin Pressure Control Unit
Auto Flight	FCC
	IRU
	TMS
	FMC
	MCP
Communications	VHF Transceivers
	VHF Control Panels
Electrical	Bus Power Control Unit
	Generator Control Unit
Engine	Engine Supervisory Limit Unit (ELC)
	EICAS
Flight Controls	Stab Trim/Aileron Lockout Module
	Yaw Damper Module
	Flap/Slat Control Unit
	Spoiler Control Module
Flight Instruments	Air Data Computer
	Airspeed Indicator
	Altitude Indicator
	RDMI
	Vertical Speed Indicator
	EFIS
Fuel	Fuel Quantity Indication System
Landing	Anti-skid System
	Autobrake Control Unit
Navigation	ILS Receivers
	Radio Altitude Transceiver
	ADF Receiver
	ATC Transponder
	DME Interrogator
	VOR Receiver
Warning	Warning Electronic Unit

Summary of Interference Identified

The aircraft-level communication and navigation receivers interference testing has been performed for four different research system configurations on the 757 ARIES. The results have been repeatable for research equipment that has been installed for different configurations. Table 4 lists the interference that has been identified for the communication receivers. The interference was of sufficient strength to either break squelch or cause audible interference with the receivers squelch disabled. The source of the interference and the location of the source are included.

Table 4. Communication Receivers Interference Identified during Aircraft-level Testing

Receiver	Source of Interference	Location of Source
VHF	Laptop computers	Various pallets installed passenger cabin
	Data Acquisition System Pallet	Passenger cabin
UHF	Heads Down Display	Forward Flight Deck
	Laptop Computer	Pallet installed in passenger cabin
	EDCP Display	Forward Flight Deck
	Research Radar R/T	Forward Electronics Bay

The laptop computers, which have not been qualified to avionics standards, installed within the passenger cabin pallets have been the most likely sources of interference in the VHF band. The results of the testing have shown the laptop computers to cause interference to the VHF receiver at nine tuned frequencies. Laptops have also been the source of interference to the UHF receivers.

Interference to the UHF receivers has been noted for equipment installed relatively close to the UHF antenna, which is located on the lower fuselage behind the radome. The research displays installed in the forward flight deck and the radar receiver/transmitter unit installed in the forward electronics bay were sources of interference to the UHF receiver.

Table 5 lists the potential interference that has been identified for the navigation receivers. The source of the interference and the location of the source are included.

Table 5. Navigation Receivers Potential Interference Identified during Aircraft-level Testing

Receiver	Source of Interference	Location of Source
Localizer	Data Acquisition System Pallet	Passenger cabin
	Research Radar R/T	Forward Electronics Bay
VOR	Data Acquisition System Pallet	Passenger cabin
	Video Tail Camera/Camera Control Unit	Vertical Stabilizer/Pallet in passenger cabin
DME	Video Telemetry Transmitters	Pallet in aft cargo bay

Potential interference to ILS Localizer from experimental radar located in the forward electronics bay has been identified. The forward electronics bay is located behind the forward pressurized bulkhead, which is where the ILS antennas are installed. In order to analyze the potential interference, the frequency spacing between the identified frequencies and the valid ILS Localizer frequencies were determined. Of the eleven potential interference signals measured, only four were within the pass band of the receiver at a valid center frequency.

The aircraft-level tests have shown a potential interference signal from the video tail camera and camera control unit to the VOR receivers. The video camera is mounted on the leading edge of the vertical stabilizer. The camera control unit is mounted in a pallet in the passenger cabin. The connecting cables run parallel to the VOR antenna's coaxial cables from the aft galley overhead through the leading edge of the vertical stabilizer. Therefore, the measured signal is most likely due to cable to cable coupling.

The signal measured at the VOR receiver is the largest in signal strength of the potential interference signals that have been identified. There has been no discernable interference to the operation of the VOR due to the potential interference signal to date. However, there have been no long-range checks of the VOR at these frequencies.

The source of the potential interference measured for the DME receivers was determined to be the video telemetry transmitters installed in the aft cargo bay. The frequencies were exactly one-half the center frequencies of the S-band transmitters. Lab testing showed that the transmitters had noise at one-half the center frequency radiating from the power and control cables. The transmitters were designed so that the one-half frequency signal was present in the transmitter at 1 Watt. This signal is then doubled in frequency and amplified depending on the desired power output. The one-half frequency signals were being picked up on the DC power and control lines within the transmitter and then were carried outside the transmitter on the cables. Therefore, when the transmitters were installed in the 757 ARIES, the control and power cables connected to the transmitter were radiating the one-half frequency signals, which are in the DME frequency band. This potential interference was mitigated by having the transmitters redesigned by the manufacturer and verified to meet radiated emissions requirements.

Conclusion

The electromagnetic interference testing for the research system installed on the 757 ARIES has been described. The testing identifies interference from the research system to the 757 ARIES communication and navigation receivers. The results have shown potential interference to the communication and navigation receivers.

The research equipment has caused discernable interference to the communication receivers. Notifying the pilots of the unusable communication frequencies mitigated this interference.

The potential interference to the navigation receivers has been mitigated by resolving the interference problem or by reporting the identified potential interference to the pilots. To date, the

pilots have not reported any anomalous readings or observable interference to the navigation receivers at the frequencies identified as potential interference during any of the ICFs or research flights.

The test results have shown good correlation between lab testing and aircraft-level testing. The aircraft-level tests have indicated that although most of the research equipment installed on the 757 ARIES has not been qualified to avionics EMI specifications, there have been relatively few cases of interference. The proximity of the installed experimental equipment to the communication or navigation receivers' antennas or cabling is a good indicator of the potential for causing interference.

References

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